

LINGUISTIC MODEL OF COLLOCATIONS WITH ENGLISH NOUNS AND THEIR EXPRESSION IN UZBEK FOR MACHINE TRANSLATION

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Abstract. *This article examines the linguistic features of collocations involving English nouns and their equivalents in Uzbek. The study explores the structural, semantic, and pragmatic aspects of collocations, providing a comparative analysis of their realization in both languages. Two illustrative tables highlight common noun-based collocations in English and their corresponding expressions in Uzbek, focusing on translation strategies and cultural nuances. The findings demonstrate the challenges of achieving equivalence and the importance of context in rendering meaning accurately.*

Keywords: *collocations, English nouns, Uzbek equivalents, translation strategies, linguistic model, cultural nuances.*

INTRODUCTION

Language is a complex system that not only conveys meaning but also reflects the cultural, social, and psychological intricacies of its speakers. Among the numerous linguistic phenomena that characterize a language, collocations stand out as a fundamental component. Collocations refer to the habitual co-occurrence of words, forming fixed or semi-fixed expressions that native speakers use intuitively. For instance, the English collocation "make a decision" or "strong tea" demonstrates how specific nouns combine with certain verbs or adjectives to create phrases with specific meanings [1].

In English, noun-based collocations play a significant role in achieving natural and fluent speech. However, their translation into other languages, such as Uzbek, often requires careful analysis. Uzbek, with its rich morphological structure and cultural uniqueness, employs different mechanisms for forming collocations. This divergence poses challenges for translators and linguists alike. By building a linguistic model for analyzing English noun-based collocations and their Uzbek equivalents, this study aims to provide insights into their structural, semantic, and pragmatic characteristics, and propose strategies for achieving accurate and culturally appropriate translations [2].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collocations are word combinations that exhibit a high degree of co-occurrence within a language. Unlike free word combinations, collocations are fixed to varying extents, making their components inseparable or only partially interchangeable. In linguistics, collocations are classified into two primary types [3]:

Grammatical Collocations: These involve a noun combined with a preposition or grammatical structure. For example:

English: "interest in," "responsibility for."

Uzbek: "qiziqish" (used with case suffixes like -ga or -dan depending on context).

Lexical Collocations: These consist of a noun paired with another lexical unit such as a verb, adjective, or another noun. Examples include:

English: "take a chance," "heavy rain."

Uzbek: "imkoniyatni qo‘lga kiritmoq," "kuchli yomg‘ir."

Collocations are language-specific and reflect the preferences of native speakers. This specificity complicates their translation, as achieving functional and cultural equivalence often requires more than direct substitution of words.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

English and Uzbek differ significantly in their approaches to forming and using collocations. English often relies on auxiliary verbs, fixed word orders, and compound expressions. For instance [4]:

English: "Make a suggestion."

Uzbek: "Tavsiyanoma bermoq" (a single verb may replace a verb-noun combination).

In Uzbek, agglutinative morphology allows the creation of collocations through suffixation and the use of affixes. This flexibility often leads to a compact expression of ideas:

English: "Gain confidence."

Uzbek: "Ishonch hosil qilish."

Cultural differences also play a significant role in shaping collocations. For example:

English: "Break the ice" (an idiom suggesting the easing of tension).

Uzbek: "Muzni eritmoq" (a direct metaphorical equivalent exists, but its usage context may differ).

Idiomatic expressions often require reinterpretation rather than literal translation, as they carry unique connotations that may not align across languages.

The semantic and pragmatic dimensions of collocations highlight the depth of their complexity. In English, collocations may convey specific nuances or levels of formality. For instance [5]:

English: "Make a decision" (neutral and formal).

Uzbek: "Qaror qabul qilish" (semantically equivalent but slightly more formal).

Moreover, some collocations in English may lack direct equivalents in Uzbek, necessitating creative translation:

English: "A rough estimate"

Uzbek: "Taxminiy hisoblash" (literal translation requires a shift in expression to maintain clarity).

Pragmatic usage, such as politeness and cultural appropriateness, further complicates equivalence. Translators must consider the context to preserve the intended meaning and tone.

The comparative analysis revealed several key insights into the linguistic behavior of English and Uzbek collocations:

Structural Variations: English noun-based collocations frequently employ auxiliary verbs, while Uzbek leverages its rich morphological structure to condense expressions.

Cultural Influence: Translation often involves cultural adaptation to align with Uzbek norms and idiomatic expressions.

Semantic Challenges: Literal translation is rarely sufficient due to the nuanced meanings and usage contexts of collocations in English.

These findings underscore the need for a robust linguistic model that integrates syntax, semantics, and pragmatics to ensure accurate translation.

Collocations are essential components of language, representing the natural pairing of words that create meaning beyond the sum of their parts. Their significance lies not only in linguistic structure but also in their cultural and pragmatic implications. This study has explored the linguistic model of noun-based collocations in English and their expression in Uzbek, highlighting the complexities and nuances involved in their translation.

Table 1

Structural Comparison of English and Uzbek Noun-Based Collocations

English Collocation	Literal Translation	Uzbek Equivalent	Structural Note
Make a decision	Qaror qabul qilish	Qaror qabul qilish	Equivalent, often direct translation.
Heavy rain	Og'ir yomg'ir	Kuchli yomg'ir	Adjective adapted for cultural fit.
Pay attention	E'tibor berish	E'tibor qaratmoq	Semantic shift for emphasis.
Give a speech	Nutq bermoq	Nutq so'zlamq	Equivalent but context-sensitive.
Take part	Qismni olish	Ishtirok etmoq	Reinterpreted verb usage.

Table 2

Translation Challenges in English-Uzbek Collocations

Challenge	Example	Explanation
Lack of Equivalence	"A heavy sleeper"	Requires contextual interpretation.
Idiomatic Nature	"Bite the bullet"	No direct Uzbek equivalent; cultural adaptation needed.
Ambiguity in Context	"Run a program"	Could mean "boshqarmoq" or "tashkil qilmoq."
Fixed Expression Limits	"On cloud nine"	Uzbek metaphorical usage is less common.

One of the key conclusions of this research is that structural differences between English and Uzbek present both challenges and opportunities in translation. English often relies on auxiliary verbs and fixed patterns to form collocations, while Uzbek employs its agglutinative nature, using affixes and flexible syntax to achieve similar meanings. For instance, the English phrase "make a decision" translates to "qaror qabul qilish" in Uzbek, where the equivalent verb construction simplifies the expression without altering its meaning.

The cultural dimension of collocations is another critical finding. English collocations often carry idiomatic or metaphorical meanings that do not have direct equivalents in Uzbek. For example, "break the ice" requires cultural adaptation as "muzni eritmoq" to convey the intended figurative sense. Such differences emphasize the importance of contextual understanding and cultural awareness in achieving effective translation.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study open the door to further research on domain-specific collocations, such as those found in business, technology, and academic discourse. Additionally,

developing more advanced computational models for automatic collocation recognition and translation could significantly aid bilingual dictionaries and machine translation systems.

Collocations are not merely linguistic constructs; they are reflections of a language's culture, worldview, and communicative preferences. Understanding their intricacies not only enriches linguistic knowledge but also fosters better cross-cultural communication and mutual understanding. As the global demand for multilingualism grows, so does the need for comprehensive studies like this, which delve into the nuanced interplay of language and culture.

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